

The Role of Organizational Commitment and Work Behavior in Mediating the Effect of Leadership on Performance (Case Study: Employee at the Education and Training Center for the Scope of BPPK, Ministry of Finance)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyse the extent to which the Leadership variable can influence the level of Employee Organizational Commitment, Employee Work Behavior and its Impact on Employee Performance at the Education and Training Centers within the BPPK Ministry of Finance. The method used in this research is a quantitative method with a data analysis method using SEM. This study proves that leadership significantly affects employee organisational commitment, employee work behaviour, and employee performance. This result means that the more effective the administration is, the more the employee's organisational commitment will be, making the employee's work behaviour better and improving employee performance to be more optimal. In addition, leadership has an indirect and significant effect on employee performance through mediating work behaviour. However, leadership has not had an indirect impact on employee performance with organisational commitment as an intervening variable.

Keywords: Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Work Behavior, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

A healthy organisation requires qualified, professional Human Resources and has a good level of organisational commitment. Human Resources in an organisation is one of the critical determinants for the effectiveness of activities carrying out the duties and functions of an organisation, including government institutions such as the Education and Training Centers.

The success of an employee's performance in a field of duty is determined mainly by the quality of competence and the level of satisfaction and comfort concerned in serving. Therefore, a good and correct understanding and application of employee work behaviour are essential to learning, according to Wexley & Gary (2005). In organisational behaviour, there are interactions and relationships between organisations on the one hand and individual behaviour on the other. More Robbin and Judge(2015), argues that organisational behavior is a field of study that investigates the influence that individuals, groups and structures have on behavior in organisations, which then aims to apply this kind of knowledge to increase the effectiveness of an organisation.

The role of the leader is very strategic to motivate employees or members of the organisation and encourage them to behave well in an effort to achieve individual, group and organisational performance. According to Wibowo(2007) and Rivai et al (2005), performance is the level of achievement of results on the implementation of certain tasks, and human resource management to achieve organisational goals (Gibson, 1996), is also the result of work achieved by a person in relation to his position in the organisation (Kast & Rosenzweig, 2002).

Research related to the influence of leadership on employee performance has so far been done. There is research which suggests that leadership has a significant positive effect on improving employee performance such as Carmeli (2003); Bierhoff & Muller (Bierhoff & Muller, 2005). This is because a leader who is able to give encouragement to his subordinates will have an impact on increasing his performance. However, the research of Shore, et al(2006), presented different results, the findings indicated that leadership had no significant effect on improving employee performance. This finding is contradictory to the findings of previous researchers due to differences in indicators, analytical methods used, and the unit of analysis, as well as from the results of the search for leadership literature as a driver of employee performance mediated by employee commitment and work behaviour. The above phenomena become even more interesting when they occur during the COVID-19 pandemic, which requires strict implementation of health protocols so that new work patterns are needed to achieve the organisational targets set.

This provides an opportunity to research the gap by conducting a more in-depth study of the variables that can function as variables determining employee performance. So that, at the same time, it can answer the contradictions in the findings that occur. These variables are leadership, organisational commitment, employee work behaviour. In the causal relationship that will be studied and analysed, the role of the variable that is believed to increase the influence of leadership on employee performance for the better is the variable of organisational commitment and employee work behaviour which is then referred to as the mediating variable. In this study, the variables used are variables that play a role in increasing the influence of leadership on employee performance,

METHOD

The population in this study were all non-structural employees (specific functional and general/implementing applicable) at each Pusdiklat within the scope of BPPK as many as 459 employees. The sampling technique used in this study is probability sampling. Using the Slovin formula at 10% precision, the percentage of allowance for inaccuracy due to sampling error that is still tolerable or desirable (Sekaran, 2007), obtained a minimum sample of 82 respondents.

They were collecting data in this study using a questionnaire technique by providing a written statement that the respondent must choose according to their characteristics related to leadership, employee organisational commitment, employee work behaviour, and employee performance from non-echelon employees in the Pusdiklat scope of BPPK. So that deployment and filling can be done more easily when implementing work. The measurement scale technique used to measure the answers to the questionnaire or questionnaire is the Likert Scale with a scale of 5. Thus, the data obtained is interval data.

This research model uses the PLS-SEM model. The initial stage tests the main analysis requirements to ensure that the measuring instrument used is suitable for measurement (valid and reliable). Testing with PLS begins with testing the measurement model (outer model) to test the construct validity and instrument reliability. The validity test is carried out to measure the ability of the research instrument to measure what it is supposed to measure (Cooper & Schindler, 2006). The construct validity test in the PLS indicator reflective model was carried out through convergent validity, discriminant validity and average variance extracted (AVE) tests. The reliability test is used to measure the consistency of the measuring instrument in measuring the concept, or it can also be used to measure the consistency of the respondent in answering the instrument. The instrument is reliable if a person's answer to the statement is consistent or stable over time. The reliability test in PLS can use the composite reliability method and Cronbach's alpha (Hartono & Abdillah, 2014)

The next step is to see the influence between variables. In the PLS-SEM, it can be seen that there are direct and indirect effects between variables. In addition, the instrument goodness test was also carried out through the outer test for the measurement model and the inner model for the structural model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of respondents broken down by gender indicate that most respondents are male. The percentage of male respondents was 63.1 per cent or 101 respondents, while the female respondents were 36.9 percent or 59 respondents. In addition, 64 certain functional employees from each detail or 40 percent, then 96 implementing employees or 60 percent.

If seen from the respondents' answers, the average value (mean) of the Leadership variable is between 4.30-4.72. This result indicates that the leadership possessed by the respondents is in a high category (average 4.30-4.72). Then the average value of the Commitment variable is in the range (1.86-4.14); this indicates that the level of commitment of the participants varies from a low level to a reasonably high category, namely 4.13. The average value of behavioral Variables is in the range of 3.29-4.31, indicating that the level of employee behaviour in the class is relatively high. The Performance Variable has a mean or an average of 4.28-4.68, which suggests that employee performance is in a very high category.

The outer model is then tested by looking at the outer loading value of each indicator. The initial results show some indicators whose outer values are below 0.6, so these indicators are removed from the model and reprocessed by issuing invalid indicators. The latest outer loading test results show that all hands are already above 0.6 to be continued with other tests.

Another method to assess discriminant validity is to look at each construct's average variance extracted (AVE) value. According to Fornell & Larcker (1981) in Ghazali (2006) stated that this measurement can be said to measure the validity of the latent variable component score, with the recommended value the AVE value must be greater than 0.50. Based on Table 1. it can be seen that the AVE value is above 0.5, which means that all latent variables used in this study are valid.

Table1. AVE Value of each Construct Variable

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Leadership	0.638
Employee Performance	0.619
Commitment	0.521
Performance Behavior	0.658

In addition to constructing validity tests, complete reliability tests were also carried out as measured by composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha from the indicator block measuring constructs with a minimum limit value of 0.7. Based on Table 2. it can be seen that the Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability values are already above 0.7, which means that all latent variables used in this study are reliable.

Table2. Construct Variable Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Leadership	0.964	0.968
Employee Performance	0.948	0.954
Commitment	0.900	0.915
Performance Behavior	0.827	0.884

Next, the inner model test for the structural model is carried out. The structural model was evaluated using R-square, Stone-Geisser Q-square test (Predictive Relevance) and Goodness of Fit (GoF). R Square adjusted value is the coefficient of determination on the endogenous construct. The adjusted r-square value of 0.288 means that the independent variable leadership and the mediating variable (Commitment and Work Behavior) can explain the dependent variable (Employee Performance) of 28.8 percent. The rest is by other variables outside the model. In addition, the square adjusted value of 0.076 means that the independent variable leadership can explain the mediating variable (commitment) by 7.6 percent, the rest by other variables outside the model. While the value of r square adjusted is 0,

Table 3. Inner Model Test

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted	Q2	GoF
Employee Performance	0.288	0.274	$= 1 - (1 - R_1^2) \dots (1 - R_k^2)$ $= 0.489$	$= \sqrt{AVE * R^2}$ $= 0.345$
Commitment	0.076	0.070		
Performance Behavior	0.223	0.218		

The Q-square value measures how well the model and its parameters generate the observed values. A Q-square value greater than 0 (zero) indicates that the model has predictive relevance, while a Q-square value less than 0 (zero) indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. In Table 3, the Q-square value is greater than 0 (zero), 0.489, meaning the model has predictive relevance.

Evaluation of the Goodness of Fit model was measured using the dependent latent variable R2 with the same interpretation as the regression. A model is good if the score is above 0.38 (perfect) and 0.30-0.37 (good enough). Based on Table 3, the GoF value = 0.345, which is significant because it is above 0.3 (it is moderately good).

The next step is to test the hypothesis; the t-statistic value generated from the PLS output is compared with the t-table value. The PLS output estimates the latent variable, a linear aggregate of indicators. The test criteria with a significance level of (a) 5% for a one-way test (positive/negative effect) is determined that if t count > t table (1.64), then H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

Table4. Direct Effect Hypothesis Testing

Direct Influence	Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values	Decision	Conclusion
Leadership -> Employee Performance	0.171	1,835	0.033	Reject Ho	Significant Take Effect
Leadership -> Commitment	0.275	3.583	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant Take Effect
Leadership -> Behavior Performance	0.472	8,774	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant Take Effect
Commitment -> Employee Performance	0.067	0.697	0.243	Don't Refuse Ho	Not Significant Take Effect
Performance Behavior -> Employee Performance	0.389	4.070	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant Take Effect

The discussion in Table 4 will discuss the relationship between variables one by one

1. The Effect of Leadership on Employee Performance.

This study found that leadership has a significant effect on employee performance, meaning that the higher or more effective leadership quality will impact the better level of employee performance. This result is based on the results of the analysis, where the coefficient of the relationship between leadership and employee performance is 0.171, the value of $t_{stat} = 1.835 > t_{table} = 1.64$ and the value of prob. value = $0.033 < \alpha = 0.05$, meaning that every 1 point increase in leadership will increase employee performance by 0.171. This result is in line with Carmeli's research(2003); Bierhoff & Muller (2005), which says that a leader who can encourage his subordinates will have an impact on increasing his performance. Respondents in this study argue that employee performance is difficult to grow if the organisation and leadership have less attention to the needs of employees in completing their work tasks. Therefore, leaders' level of self-control and good attention encourage subordinates. They should always be maintained; leaders who can meet the needs of assistants become the expectations of associates as shown in the description of respondents' answers that reach the highest std (standard deviation) value of 0, 72.

2. The Effect of Leadership on Organizational Commitment

This study found that leadership has a direct and significant impact on employee organizational commitment with a coefficient of 0.275, $t_{stat} = 3.583 > t_{table} = 1.64$ and prob value = $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This result means that a 1 point increase in leadership will increase commitment by 0.275 points assuming other variables are constant. This result means that the higher the level of leadership of a leader in carrying out organisational strategy, the better the employee's organisational commitment will be, employees will feel comfortable carrying out their duties and do not wish to leave the institution or institution that houses them. This result is in line with the research of Kerdpitak & Boonrattanakittibhumi (2020), who said that an organisation that cares about its employees is considered a soft HR policy and limited or rigid behaviour is indicated by hard HR. The study recommends that organisations develop strategic practices and HR policies to maintain organisational commitment among employees and increase performance because low organisational commitment tends to increase turnover.

Jansen (1993) added that if employee commitment is low, it can trigger unfavourable employee behaviour, for example, riots which further impact is a decline in the organisation's reputation, loss of trust. A different result is a decrease in company profits. Meanwhile, from an employee point of view, high employee commitment will improve the employee's career. In terms of the company, employees who have a high commitment to the organisation will contribute to workforce stability. Respondents argued in answer to open-ended questions that organisational commitment is a value that needs to be maintained to motivate employees to achieve the organisation's vision and mission. On the other hand, some think that organisational commitment is required, but employee career development must also be considered. Therefore, awareness, social awareness, and a good level of self-control towards a leader's emotions are needed so that the organisation can achieve its best performance.

3. Influence of Leadership on Work Behavior

This study found that leadership has a direct and significant impact on improving employee work behaviour. This result can be seen with the correlation coefficient of 0.472, the value of $t_{stat} = 8.774 > t_{table} = 1.64$ and the importance of prob. value = $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$, which means an increase of 1 point in leadership will increase performance behaviour by 0.472 points assuming other variables. Constant. The better the administration carried out by a leader in managing his team, or work unit will directly impact the quality of work behaviour of employees who become subordinates. Thus, it is expected that employees will become more concerned about their work duties, work with enthusiasm and sincerity without being burdened. This result is in line with the research of Wexley & Yuki (2005), who says that in organisational behaviour (which is interpreted as leadership), there are interactions and relationships between organisations on the one hand and individual behaviour on the other. Respondents in this study argue that leaders face various types of subordinates with different cultural, religious and character backgrounds; leaders must be good at managing this diversity. Therefore, a good and correct understanding and application of employee work behaviour are essential to be adequately studied by a leader to apply the appropriate leadership style to create subordinates who have excellent and intelligent work behaviour.

4. The Influence of Commitment to Employee Performance

This study found that commitment does not directly affect employee performance with a coefficient of 0.067, $t_{stat} = 0.697 < t_{table} = 1.64$ and prob value = $0.243 > \alpha = 0.05$. So, it is indicated that there is not enough evidence that an increase in commitment will increase performance by 0.067 points with the assumption that other variables are constant. This result is in line with research conducted by Carmeli (2003), which concludes that leadership and work attitudes affect employee performance, while leadership and organisational commitment do not have a positive effect on employee performance. Respondents in this study argued that related to organisational commitment; employee organisational commitment was needed to create synergy in achieving organisational goals; employee commitment to the organisation raised the employee's enthusiasm to seek innovation in completing work. This result is in line with the respondents' answers. In the description of answers which in this study tend to realise that the problems that exist in the organisation are essentially employee problems with the acquisition of the highest std (standard deviation) value of 1, 28 so that employee awareness arises that organisational commitment must be

maintained and maintained with full responsibility (Affective Commitment). Therefore, leaders and organisations should always maintain employee organisational commitment at a high level by paying attention as needed.

5. The Influence of Work Behavior on Employee Performance

This study found that work behaviour has a direct and significant positive effect on employee performance with a coefficient of 0.389, the value of $t_{stat} = 4.070 > t_{table} = 1.64$ and the value of prob. value = $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$, this means the better the work behaviour of employees. Can improve employee performance with the assumption that other variables are constant. This result is in line with research conducted by Carmeli (2003) concluded that leadership and work attitudes affect employee performance. Behaviour is generally unique and even tends to be complicated; this uniqueness and complexity of behaviour often make it difficult for a leader to understand his subordinates' behaviour. However, by understanding human behaviour or individual employees, you will understand how an organisation behaves and functions. Respondents in this study argued that two other things are indications for employee involvement in a job other than a necessity. First, the employee in question has high creativity and innovation, so the existing work system is always exciting to develop or simplify. Second, the work system in the office is not yet sound, so it requires employee involvement to find gaps that can be improved together; the participation of teamwork in a unit significantly affects employee work behaviour. This result is in line with the respondents' answers which show the highest std (standard deviation) value of 1.10 on the item employees feel at home working at the Ministry of Finance. Therefore, leaders must first understand how these individual employees can behave and function as expected by the Ministry of Finance organisation. Ten on the item employees feel at home working at the Ministry of Finance agency. Therefore, leaders must first understand how these individual employees can behave and function as expected by the Ministry of Finance organisation. Ten on the item employees feel at home working at the Ministry of Finance agency. Therefore, leaders must first understand how these individual employees can behave and function as expected by the Ministry of Finance organisation.

Table5.Indirect Effect Test Table

Indirect Influence	Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values	Result	Conclusion
Leadership -> Commitment -> Employee Performance	0.018	0.651	0.258	No reject Ho	not yet significant effect
Leadership -> Performance Behavior -> Employee Performance	0.184	3.688	0.000	Reject Ho	significant effect

The results of the Mediation Test in Table 5 show that the Indirect Effect coefficient of the Leadership variable has not had an indirect and positive insignificant effect on Employee Performance through commitment mediation with a coefficient of 0.018, $t_{stat} = 0.651 < t_{table} = 1.64$ and prob value. value= $0.258 > \alpha=0.05$. This result means that the high quality of leadership has not been able to improve employee performance through commitment as a mediating/intervening variable with the assumption that other variables are constant.

While the coefficient of indirect influence of leadership has an indirect and significant effect on employee performance through mediation of work behavior with a coefficient of 0.180, $t_{stat} = 3.688 > 1 t_{table} = 1.64$ and p-value = $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This result indicates that a higher leadership level can improve employee performance with employee work behaviour as a mediating variable, assuming that other variables are constant.

CONCLUSION

This study proves that leadership significantly affects employee organisational commitment, employee work behaviour, and employee performance. It means that the more influential the leadership is, the more the employee's organisational commitment will be, making the employee's work behaviour better and improving employee performance to be more optimal.

While the indirect influence of leadership, the study results prove that leadership has an indirect and significant effect on employee performance through mediating work behaviour.

On the other hand, leadership does not indirectly affect employee performance, with organisational commitment as an intervening variable. This result means that leadership effectiveness does not increase performance through employee organisational commitment as a mediating/intervening variable. In this study, respondents tend to realise that the problems that exist in the organisation are essentially employee problems with the highest std (standard deviation) value of 1.28 so that employee awareness arises that organisational commitment must be maintained and maintained with full responsibility (Affective Commitment).

Based on the results of the research that has been done, some suggestions that can be recommended are that a leader's ability to understand and apply a good understanding of organisational commitment, work behaviour and employee performance is needed to use the appropriate leadership style to create subordinates who have good work behaviour.

Good and smart. Therefore, leaders who are skilled in dealing with various types of associates with different cultural, religious and character backgrounds become more suitable; leaders should manage this diversity.

In addition, a solid and effective leadership role is needed by developing a harmonious and effective working relationship pattern to maintain organisational commitment and good employee work behaviour so that they are always at a reasonable level, to be able to improve further employee performance, which in turn can enhance organisational performance optimally.

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